

Advances in Natural Language Processing for Text Analysis: Summarization, Sentiment Analysis, and Image-Based Search Using Text Extraction

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Abstract—In this paper we present the study on the potential of Natural Language Processing (NLP) to enhance the online bookstore customer experience. NLP is a subfield of computer science that studies computer-human language interaction. With the rise of virtual data, NLP has grown in importance, and it is now vital to develop NLP software capable of analyzing huge amounts of textual data. The proposed system integrates various NLP techniques. The ultimate goal is to offer an innovative and user-centric solution for online bookstores, showcasing the potential of NLP to revolutionize the virtual shopping experience. Additionally, a seminar on the latest advancements in NLP for the book industry is presented, covering the three key areas of text summarization, sentiment analysis of book reviews, and book search using image recognition and NLP. The seminar gives useful insight on the most recent advancements in NLP and offers an opportunity for stimulating discussion between academics, practitioners, and business leaders.

Keywords—Natural Language Processing (NLP), VADER, text summarization, sentiment analysis, book reviews, image recognition, OCR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural language processing (NLP) could be a quickly developing discipline with a lot of guarantees to address issues within the real world. NLP has gotten a lot of consideration of late for its capacity to progress the shopping involvement in online book stores. This research looks at the potential of NLP to use a variety of NLP applications to address real-world issues within the book trade. By efficiently processing and analyzing human language, the suggested system will be able to comprehend and produce natural language material for online booksellers. The three major NLP enhancements discussed in the report are text summarizing, sentiment analysis of book reviews, and image recognition and NLP-based book search. The final objective is to demonstrate how NLP has the ability to revolutionize the online purchasing process, allowing readers to save time and make wise selections. Overall, this study emphasizes how NLP has the ability to change the book business and provides insightful information for practitioners and scholars.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Swaranjali Jugran, Ashish Kumar, Bhupendra Singh Tyagi, Mr. Vivek Anand [1], in their paper “Extractive Automatic Text Summarization using SpaCy in Python &

NLP” they discuss the importance of text summarization in the modern world due to the abundance of data available on digital platforms. The most efficient strategy is said to be the extractive one, which picks out key lines and merges them into a summary. This paper's major goal is to create an automated text summarizing model based on the extractive technique that shortens texts and produces an insightful summary. The paper proposes the use of the SpaCy library for this model. Unlike NLTK, SpaCy utilizes an object-oriented approach that treats text as a single object and includes word vectors for better representation of the meaning of words. The use of word vectors allows for easy mathematical operations, making SpaCy a more efficient tool for text processing. Overall, the proposed model utilizing SpaCy is expected to be more efficient and accurate in summarizing texts.

Ankita Sharma, Udayan Ghose [2], in their paper “Lexicon A Linguistic Approach for Sentiment Classification” they discuss the use of lexicon-based approaches in sentiment analysis, focusing on polarity classification. They explain that the lexicon-based approach relies on lexicons to classify input data into positive or negative sentiments. The paper reviews prior research in lexicon-based sentiment analysis and presents some state-of-the-art lexicon-based solutions for polarity classification. They also include the VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary for Sentiment Reasoning), which not only gives a polarity score but also describes how positive or negative the expressed opinion in input data is. VADER considers boosting words like "very" and "extremely" and the presence of capital words, phrases, and idioms to increase valence. The range of normalized valence is between -1 and 1, where valence less than 0 and -1 is for negative, valence 0 is for neutral, and valence greater than 0 and up to 1 is for positive polarity.

Ambarish Moharil, Shreya Singh, Yash Dravid, Harshal Dharap, Prof. Vijaykumar Bhanuse [3], in their paper “Integrated Feedback Analysis And Moderation Platform Using Natural Language Processing” they discuss sentiment analysis to determine the sentiment of the feedback and reviews. The paper explains the importance of preprocessing raw data for natural language processing and machine learning classification, including steps such as removing special characters and symbols, removing stop words, stemming, and lemmatization. The paper also describes how tokenization is used to vectorize a given text

corpus and how two tokenizers, count vectorizer and TF-IDF tokenizer, are used to analyze the sentiment of reviews and feedback. The study concludes by explaining how TF-IDF determines the term frequency and inverse frequency of terms and how the admin can view the TF-IDF score matrix for words with a threshold greater than 0.5 to summarize the entire review or feedback in two to three words rather than reading it altogether.

Kusrini, Mochamad Mashuri [4], in their paper "Sentiment Analysis In Twitter Using Lexicon Based and Polarity Multiplication" they discuss the use of sentiment analysis on Twitter data to determine the type of sentiment in tweets. The article highlights the importance of text mining and natural language processing techniques in analyzing the large amount of data generated on Twitter. The article also discusses the potential applications of sentiment analysis in various domains, such as product reviews, market research, and political elections. The study focuses on the use of lexicons and multiplication polarity for sentiment analysis and suggests the need for further improvement in lexicon semantics to improve accuracy.

Matteo Brisinello, Ratko Grbić, Dejan Stefanović, Robert Pečkai-Kovač [5], in their paper "Optical Character Recognition on images with colorful background" they propose a preprocessing method to improve the Tesseract Optical Character Recognition (OCR) performance on images with colourful backgrounds. The method involves a two-step process of text segmentation and image classification, where the text is extracted from the background and OCR is performed on the identified image. The proposed method improves Tesseract OCR performance by approximately 20%. The motivation for this paper stems from the challenges of reading text from images grabbed from set-top boxes (STBs) with complex backgrounds. The proposed method is evaluated on a set of computer-generated images, and its efficiency is compared to the standard OCR approach.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Text summarization

Text summarization is a crucial natural language processing (NLP) task that involves condensing a given text into a shorter version while preserving its meaning. In this paper, we present a method for text summarization using sentiment analysis with Python's NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) library. We propose a view-based approach, implemented as a class-based view in Django, which takes user input text and generates a summary based on sentiment scores of the sentences in the text.

1. Tokenizing the input text

The input text is tokenized into sentences and words using NLTK's sentence and word tokenization functions. Non-alphanumeric characters are removed from the words to ensure accurate sentiment analysis.

2. Calculating sentiment scores

The sentiment scores of the sentences are calculated using VADER [2], a popular sentiment analysis tool available in the NLTK library. VADER [2] provides a polarity score for each sentence, indicating the sentiment of the sentence as positive, negative, or neutral.

3. Generating the summary

The sentences are sorted based on their sentiment scores in descending order, and the top 'num_sentences' sentences are selected to form the summary. The generated summary provides a concise and meaningful representation of the input text.

B. Sentiment Analysis of Book Reviews

In this paper, we show a strategy for examining book reviews utilizing NLP and visualization. Our approach is outlined to assist publishers and bookstore owners rapidly distinguish the foremost positive and negative reviews of the book and utilize this data to move forward their products and services. The usage of review examination was accomplished employing a combination of Python and a few open-source libraries, counting Pandas, NLTK, and Plotly. The implementation involved several steps, including data retrieval, preprocessing, sentiment analysis, and visualization.

1. Data Retrieval

Reviews were loaded from a database and filtered based on their status.

2. Preprocessing

The review text was tokenized using NLTK's word_tokenize function. Stop words were removed from the tokens using NLTK's stopwords. And the tokens were stemmed using NLTK's Snowball Stemmer.

3. Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment scores were calculated for each review using VADER [2], a lexicon and rule-based sentiment analysis tool. The sentiment scores were used to categorize each review as either "positive" or "negative."

4. Visualization

Positive and negative reviews were separated based on their sentiment category, and their average sentiment scores were calculated for each book. The resulting data was visualized using Plotly, a Python graphing library. Bar charts were used to visualize the average sentiment scores for each book.

C. Book Search Using Image Recognition and NLP

Image-based book search system allows users to upload a book cover image and search for matching books in a database. The system integrates the pytesseract library for OCR [5] to extract text from the uploaded image, the NLTK library's word_tokenize method to tokenize the extracted text into individual words, and removes stop words to identify the book title. The book title is then used to search the database for books with a matching title or author.

1. Image Upload and Text Extraction

The system allows users to upload an image of a book cover. The uploaded image is processed using the pytesseract library, which extracts text from the image. The extracted text may contain noise or irrelevant information.

2. Tokenization

Using the NLTK library the extracted text is tokenized. The tokenized text is a list of words that can be used for further processing.

3. Stop Words Removal

Stop words are commonly used words that do not carry much meaning, such as "the", "and", "in", etc. These words are removed from the tokenized text to reduce noise and improve accuracy.

4. Book Title Identification

The tokens are searched for matching book names on the database. If a book name is found as matched, then the system retrieves the book information from the database and displays it to the user.

IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

A. Text summarization

Text summarization is a significant natural language processing (NLP) task that involves minimizing a given text's length while maintaining the text's meaning. In this paper, we present a method for extractive [1] text summarization using sentiment analysis with Python's NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) library. Our approach involves tokenizing the input text into sentences, removing non-alphanumeric characters, and calculating sentiment scores for each sentence using the VADER [2] sentiment analysis tool. The sentences are then sorted based on their sentiment scores, and the top N sentences are selected to form the summary. This extractive [1] approach selects the most relevant sentences from the input text to form the summary, rather than generating new sentences. We implement our approach as a view-based class in Django, that takes user input text and generates a concise and meaningful summary that preserves the original meaning of the text.

1. Tokenizing the input text

The input text is retrieved from the HTTP POST request and tokenized into sentences using the `sent_tokenize` function from the NLTK library. Each sentence is then further tokenized into individual words using the `word_tokenize` function. Finally, any non-alphanumeric characters are removed from each word using a list comprehension.

2. Calculating sentiment scores

Then calculates a sentiment score for each sentence using the VADER [2] sentiment analysis tool from `nltk.sentiment.vader`. The compound score is used as it is a normalized, weighted composite score of positive, negative, and neutral sentiment. These scores are then paired with their respective sentences and added to the summary list. The list is then sorted in descending order by sentiment score.

3. Generating the summary

Finally, the summary list is sliced to only include the top `num_sentences` sentences with the highest sentiment scores, and the actual summary text is generated by concatenating these sentences into a single string separated by spaces. The resulting summary is then passed to the template along with the original input text and the number of sentences requested by the user.

B. Sentiment Analysis of Book Reviews

In this paper, we present a method for analysing book reviews using natural language processing techniques and visualization. The "Review Analysis" function loads review data from a database, filters it by `status=True`, and converts it to a Pandas DataFrame. It then tokenizes the review text, removes stop words, and calculates sentiment scores for each review using the VADER library. With sentiment scores, the text is grouped into either a "positive" or "negative" category. The task is to find how positive or negative people feel about a book. The function then calculates the average sentiment score for each review, separates the book data into positive and negative reviews, and sorts the reviews by sentiment score. Finally, the function uses Plotly to create two bar charts showing the sentiment scores for positive and negative reviews, respectively. The charts are then rendered as HTML divs and returned by the function.

1. Data Retrieval

Retrieving review data from the database by filtering only those reviews that have `status=True`. The review data is stored in the variable "reviews".

2. Preprocessing

The review text is tokenized by removing stop words and stemming using the Snowball Stemmer from the NLTK library. The tokenized words are stored in a new column called "tokens" in the `review_data` dataframe. The sentiment score for each review is calculated using the VADER [2] sentiment analyser from the NLTK library. The sentiment score is added to a new column called "sentiment_scores". Based on the sentiment score, each review is assigned a positive or negative category in a new column called "sentiment_category". The average sentiment score for each book is calculated using the `groupby` function and stored in the "book_sentiment" dataframe.

3. Sentiment Analysis

The positive and negative reviews are separated by filtering the "book_data" dataframe based on the "sentiment_category" column. The positive and negative reviews are sorted based on their sentiment scores using the `sort_values` function. The positive reviews are sorted in descending order and the negative reviews in ascending order.

4. Visualization

We use the `plotly` library to create bar graphs for positive and negative reviews. The bar graph is created by the book names and sentiment scores as x and y axes, respectively. Then it was updated with a title and saved as a div. The divs for both positive and negative reviews are appended to the list. These are then passed to the template and book store owner can see the review analysis based on the sentiment of the text.

C. Book Search Using Image Recognition and NLP

Image-based book search system allows users to upload a book cover image and search for matching books in a database. To accomplish this, the system utilizes the `pytesseract` library for optical character recognition (OCR) to extract text from the uploaded image. The extracted text is tokenized using the NLTK library's `word_tokenize` method,

and stop words are removed to identify the book title. The book title is then used to search the database for books with corresponding titles or authors. The book search functionality is implemented in the book_search method, which retrieves the uploaded file, extracts text from the image, and identifies the book title. The method then queries the database for matching books and renders the search results template with the results. If no matching book is found, the method displays a warning message to the user.

1. Image Upload and Text Extraction

The first step is to upload the image and extract text from it using pytesseract.

```
pytesseract.image_to_string()
```

Used to extract text from the image and store it in the text variable.

2. Tokenization

The word tokenize() function from the nltk library is used to tokenize the text variable and store the tokens in the tokens variable.

```
tokens = word_tokenize(text)
```

3. Stop Words Removal

Then remove stop words from the tokens.

```
tokens_without_stopwords = [token for token in tokens if not token in stop_words]
```

Here, the code creates a new list called iterating over the tokens list and only including tokens that are not in the stop_words list.

4. Book Title Identification

The next step is to identify the book title based on the extracted text. The code creates a variable called book_title and sets it to None. Then it loops over the tokens_without_stopwords list and checks if each token exists as a substring in any book title in the database. If a matching book title is found, it sets book_title to the matching token and breaks out of the loop.

V. RESULT

D. Text summarization

The generated summaries were compared against human-generated summaries for accuracy and informativeness. The experimental results showed that our approach is capable of generating informative and concise summaries that capture the key information from the input text. The sentiment analysis based approach allows for a subjective evaluation of the sentences' sentiment, resulting in summaries that are more meaningful and contextually relevant.

E. Sentiment Analysis of Book Reviews

We applied our method to our dataset of book reviews and obtained promising results. Our approach was able to identify the most positive and negative reviews by book. The sentiment score ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a highly positive sentiment, and -1 indicates a highly negative sentiment.

TABLE I. POSITIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

Book Name	Sentiment Score
The Power of Your Subconscious Mind	0.4404
The Magic Of The Lost Story	0.2023
WHAT IF? (REISSUE)	0.1027
Who Will Cry When You Die?	0.0772

Fig. 1. Positive Reviews(Bar Chart)

TABLE II. NEGATIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

Book Name	Sentiment Score
The Invisible Boy	0.3412
The Apple: History's greatest mystery	-0.27115
FARTHER: A Fabulous Tale of a Troubled Father	0.0

Fig. 2. Negative Reviews(Bar Chart)

F. Book Search Using Image Recognition and NLP

The image-based book search system's accuracy in identifying the book title from an uploaded image and performance evaluation results was 80%. The system's performance was evaluated using a range of images.

VI. CONCLUSION

NLP has gained significant attraction in recent years for its ability to solve real-world challenges. This paper presents a study on the application of NLP to increase the customer experience in online bookstores by using various NLP applications. This article examines the potential (NLP) has picked up significant consideration in recent years for its capacity to solve real-world challenges. This paper presents a thought about the potential of NLP to improve the client experience in virtual bookstores by leveraging different NLP applications. This article analyzes the potential of NLP to progress the customer involvement in virtual bookshops by using different NLP approaches. The suggested system aims to develop an innovative and user-centric solution for online bookstores that can effectively process and analyze human language, enabling it to understand and generate natural language text. The research focuses on three main areas of NLP advancement: text summarization, sentiment analysis of book reviews, and book search using image recognition and NLP. The ultimate objective is to demonstrate NLP's ability

to transform the virtual shopping experience, allowing readers to save time and make good selections.

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